

**Antecedent And Outcomes Of Job Embeddedness In Healthcare
Sector: A Mediated Model**

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Abstract

This research strives to establish that how the role of job embeddedness explains effect of inclusive leadership on two dependent variables: organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) and employee resilience (ER) in nurses working in Rawalpindi and Islamabad, Pakistan in times when organization's ability to retain skilled healthcare professionals is becoming a significant challenge. Quantitative data is obtained by using a cross-sectional survey from 250 nursing staffs through self-administered questionnaires. A systematic sampling technique is employed to ensure a structured and representative selection of participants from the target population and data is analyzed using SPSS to test hypothesized relationships. Finally, this work shows that inclusive leadership leads to increased job embeddedness which when promoted increases overall OCB and resilience in workforce. Thus, the study demonstrates significance of approach that is based on idea of inclusive leadership that fosters a positive organisational climate and enhances exerted pressure on employees in regard to their commitment to the appointed positions. It presents guidelines for hospitals and healthcare organizations willing to enhance their leadership practices to foster employees' job embeddedness aiming at staffing a highly engaged workforce, thereby providing a practical and theoretical value to this line of research.

Keywords: Inclusive Leadership; Job Embeddedness; Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB); Employee Resilience; Healthcare Workforce Retention;

Introduction

The modern organizational landscape is becoming complex as companies aim to improve worker performance and retention in fast-paced, competitive industries. Sustainable success requires an understanding of the elements that affect

organizational effectiveness and personnel retention. The present study investigates the antecedent and effects of job embeddedness, with a focus on the role that inclusive leadership plays in influencing job embeddedness, which in turn affects employee resilience and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Inclusive leadership means having the ability to lead a diverse group of people while demonstrating respect for each person's unique characteristics without biasness. Inclusion has been described as "the degree to which an employee perceives that he or she is an esteemed member of the workgroup through experiencing treatment that satisfies his or her needs for belongingness and uniqueness" (Zheng et al., 2017). Therefore, the research questions of our study are: Does there is the relationship between job embeddedness and OCB? Does there is the relationship between inclusive leadership and OCB?

According to Carmeli et al. (2010), inclusive leadership is characterized by actions that show openness, accessibility and availability to every team member, creating a work atmosphere where staff members feel appreciated and included. It has been demonstrated that this leadership style has a major impact on workers' psychological safety, level of engagement, and general job happiness (Randel et al., 2018). This study attempts to understand how inclusive behaviors by leaders improve job embeddedness among employees, resulting in favourable organizational outcomes, by looking at inclusive leadership as an antecedent. Does there is the relationship between inclusive leadership and employee resilience?

According to Mitchell et al. (2001), job embeddedness is a concept that characterizes the various factors that maintain an employee's attachment to their work, including connections to other individuals and activities, the perception of fit between the job and the company, and the sacrifices made while leaving. According to research, job embeddedness significantly lowers both intended and actual turnover (Lee et al., 2014). Job embeddedness is the collection of forces that influence employee retention (Ng and Feldman, 2013). Nonetheless, there is not enough research on the mediating function that job embeddedness plays in the connection between inclusive leadership and favourable organizational outcomes like OCB and employee resilience. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is defined as activity outside the formal incentive system that is not expressly encouraged (Ali et al., 2022). By investigating how work embeddedness mediates the impacts of inclusive leadership on these outcomes, this study seeks to close this gap. Does there is the relationship between job embeddedness and employee resilience? Does Job embeddedness positively mediate the relationship between its antecedent which is inclusive leadership and its outcomes that are OCB and employee resilience?

Voluntary actions that advance the organization but are not explicitly acknowledged by the official incentive structure are referred to as organizational citizenship behavior, or OCB (Organ, 1988). According to Masten (2001), employee resilience is the ability to overcome hardship and continue or resume high performance levels. The prosperity of the organization and the welfare of its employees depend on both concepts. Examining these as results of job embeddedness offers insights into how inclusive leadership, via the mediating role of job embeddedness.

One of the challenges is that Pakistan is suffering from a critical shortage of nurses. According to the Pakistan Nursing Council (PNC), the nurse-to-patient ratio is alarmingly low, with only one nurse for every 50 patients, far below the World Health Organization's recommended ratio of 1:10. Among these, two critical issues that significantly impact the efficiency and effectiveness of healthcare delivery are the lack of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) and employee resilience among nurses. OCB, which refers to the voluntary, extra-role activities that contribute to organizational effectiveness, is notably absent and employee resilience, encompassing an individual attribute that guarantees adaptation to adversity, is low among Pakistani nurses (Javed & Khan, 2021). That is why it is very important to addressing the antecedent and outcomes of job embeddedness among nurses in Pakistan for improving OCB and employee resilience, enhancing nurse retention, and ensuring better healthcare delivery. Employees will be successful in health care if they are bounded to their jobs and are willing to collaborate, aid colleagues, give advice, participate effectively, provide good service and make good use of their work time. This behavior is referred to as organizational citizenship behavior (OCB).

So far, many public concerns have focused on delayed service and rude nurses in service. This is due to a lack of professionalism in carrying out tasks and obligations, such as inadequate planning, monitoring, and control, resulting in discontent. Aside from the aforementioned causes, task stress, a lack of organizational incentive, and inclusive leadership all contribute to these issues. This issue can be problematic since it is tied to the development of staff competences, which can have an influence on individual performance and, consequently, organizational performance. This point to a lack of staff loyalty. Employees with OCB are more likely to be loyal to their employers and to feel comfortable and safe at work. Employee OCB behavior is needed and needs special attention and appreciation so that employees remain motivated through inclusive leadership.

Despite significant progress in healthcare access, the healthcare industry in Pakistan faces a critical shortage of nurses, with a nurse-to-patient ratio far below WHO recommendations. This shortage adversely affects patient outcomes and healthcare delivery. Additionally, low levels of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) and employee resilience among nurses exacerbate the problem, leading to issues such as delayed services and perceived rudeness, largely due to high stress, inadequate organizational support, and poor leadership. Addressing the antecedent and outcomes of job embeddedness is essential for enhancing nurse retention, improving OCB, and ensuring better healthcare delivery in Pakistan.

The aim of this study is to examine at the mediation role of job embeddedness in the relationships between inclusive leadership, and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and employee resilience. By investigating these associations, the study hopes to get a better understanding of the mechanisms by which antecedent impact OCB, especially via changing employees' feelings of job embeddedness.

Theory and Hypotheses

Organization Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Ozyilmaz et al. (2018) emphasize that employee assistance—also referred to as discretionary behavior or supplemental roles—is a good technique for enhancing business effectiveness within the firm. This includes performing work outside of obligations, significant tasks, and job status functions. The productivity of the organization rises when its employees exhibit OCB behavior. Helping others, offering to help with extra chores, and following rules and regulations at work are examples of OCB behavior. OCB will inevitably rise in a company whose workers are motivated to support one another and really interested in achieving corporate objectives. Positive deviant behavior is what makes these actions valuable to workers (Hidayati et al., 2022).

Employee Resilience

Three organizational factors have been identified thus far as having an impact on resilient employee behaviors: learning culture, supportive team and organization, and leadership (Hamid, 2025; Näswall et al., 2015). According to research, an organization's support is by far the biggest factor influencing employee resilience (Hamid & Abbas, 2025; Kuntz et al., 2016). This means that an organization's ability to support employees is crucial for them to adopt resilient behaviors (Nilakant et al., 2016).

Relationship Between Inclusive Leadership and OCB

Previous studies have shown that tasks, organizational characteristics, and leadership are OCB antecedent (Podsakoff et al., 2000). Numerous studies have demonstrated the diverse effects of different antecedent on OCB (Spitzmuller et al., 2008). Nonetheless, Aryee et al. (2012) found that workers exhibit both OCB when they trust their leaders—a critical aspect of social interaction. On the other hand, OCB has been connected to perceived organizational support brought about by supportive leadership (Moorman et al., 2014). There are three ways that inclusive leadership may enhance employees' OCB. As per the social exchange theory (Blau, 2021; Hamid & Awhinawhi, 2025), supportive behaviors of inclusive leaders help workers to feel that they have been treated favourably, which in turn encourages them to act in a reciprocal manner towards the leader and the company (Wang, 2008). Therefore, it can be hypothesized that:

H₁: There is a positive relationship between inclusive leadership and OCB

Relationship Between Inclusive Leadership and Employee Resilience

According to Javed et al. (2019), inclusive leadership lessens the emotional weariness that might compromise resilience and promotes a feeling of belonging. Employees are inspired to persevere in the face of difficulties because they feel essential to the success of the company because they feel included and connected (Hsu & Huynh, 2023; Shamas et al., 2025). Enhancing resilience is also significantly aided by the empowerment that inclusive leaders bring. By allowing employees to participate in

decision-making and promoting autonomy, inclusive leaders empower their workforce. Employee empowerment increases resilience and self-assurance in one's capacity to overcome challenges. According to Shore et al. (2011), inclusive leadership increases worker empowerment, which boosts workers' resilience. Employees with higher empowerment are more proactive and have greater ability to overcome obstacles.

H₂: There is a positive relationship between inclusive leadership and employee resilience.

Relationship Between Inclusive leadership and job embeddedness

In certain aspects, inclusive leadership is comparable to servant leadership, such as demonstrating a readiness to hear their subordinates' opinions, attend to their needs, and assist them in completing their work (Masih et al., 2025; Van Dierendonck, 2010). Additionally, inclusive leadership shares characteristics with participatory leadership, such as the use of shared decision-making processes and follower meetings, and it also shares characteristics with transformational leadership (Mitchell et al., 2015), such as motivating subordinates (Choi et al., 2015; Iqbal et al., 2021). Unlike these three concepts, inclusive leadership concentrates on circumstances including status, power dynamics, and a major focus on actions that recognize the importance of variety in other people's perspectives (Rodriguez, 2018). Therefore,

H₃: There is a positive relationship between inclusive leadership and job embeddedness.

Relationship Between Job Embeddedness and OCB

It is believed that being job embedded is advantageous for firms and people alike. More embedded workers put in more effort, execute their tasks more effectively, don't miss work as often, are more likely to participate in positive organizational behaviors, and have greater levels of individual adaptive performance (Kanten et al., 2020; Shah et al., 2025). Employee integration into their work is facilitated by positive interactions with supervisors (Erkutlu et al., 2019). According to earlier research, employees' organizational job embeddedness is influenced by a leader's actions. Authentic leadership (Aurangzeb et al., 2024; Chafra et al., 2016), transformative leadership (Amankwaa, 2019) and empowering leadership (Erkutlu et al., 2022) are a few examples of these traits. Therefore, it can be hypothesized that:

H₄: There is a positive relationship between job embeddedness and OCB.

Job Embeddedness as a Mediator between Inclusive Leadership and OCB

According to recent studies, the association between inclusive leadership and OCB may be mediated by job embeddedness, a notion that includes the elements that bind workers to their employment and organizations (Hom et al., 2012). According to the job embeddedness hypothesis, individuals are more likely to display OCB if they feel integrated into their work environment through elements including social ties, fit with the company, and perceived sacrifice (Mitchell et al., 2012). Previous research suggests that inclusive leadership approaches can increase employees' commitment

and sense of belonging, which improves their embeddedness in their jobs (Abbasi, Khan, & Hamid, 2025; Shore et al., 2019). Workers are more likely to feel appreciated and supported at work when they see their leaders as inclusive, which strengthens their bonds to their positions and coworkers. Additionally, it has been discovered that job embeddedness has a beneficial impact on OCB by fostering organizational commitment, staff retention, and cooperation and collaboration (Lee et al., 2015). Therefore, it can be hypothesized that:

H₅: Job embeddedness positively mediates the relationship between inclusive leadership and OCB.

Relationship between Job Embeddedness and Employee Resilience

Resilience-enhancing proactive actions are fostered by work embeddedness. Embedded workers are more likely to take steps to safeguard their investments in the company, like actively supporting organizational objectives, networking inside the organization, and looking for possibilities for professional growth (Holtom et al., 2008). These actions not only increase their commitment to the company but also improve their abilities and resources, which makes it easier for them to adjust to shifting conditions and obstacles. Additionally, job embeddedness raises the sense of stability and security that workers feel in their positions. Resilience requires continuity and predictability, both of which are provided by this stability. When there is uncertainty or organizational change, employees who feel safe in their roles are more likely to continue being productive and dedicated (Erez, 2001).

H₆: There is a positive relationship between job embeddedness and employee resilience

Job Embeddedness as a Mediator between Inclusive Leadership and Employee Resilience

Since job embeddedness increases employees' dedication to their jobs and the business, it serves as a mediator in the interaction between inclusive leadership and employee resilience. Workers are more likely to feel embedded in their work if they believe that the company culture, their personal beliefs, and their career objectives are strongly aligned (Lee et al., 2004). This alignment increases their drive to persevere and stay devoted in the face of adversity. Moreover, employment embeddedness promotes the growth of solid interpersonal connections within the company. Fostering a supporting network among staff members is facilitated by inclusive leaders that encourage cooperation, trust, and teamwork. These social ties offer direction, encouragement, and emotional support—all of which are essential for enhancing workers' resilience (Mitchell et al., 2001). Thus, it is hypothesized that:

H₇: Job embeddedness positively mediates the relationship inclusive leadership and employee resilience

The Job Embeddedness Theory (Mitchell et al., 2001) explains how employees' connections with their job and organization influence their retention and engagement. It highlights three factors: fit, the alignment between an employee's values, career goals, and the organization's culture; linkages, the formal and informal relationships

that strengthen their ties to the organization; and sacrifice, the perceived losses, such as benefits or connections, they would face if they left. Together, these elements explain why employees remain committed to their roles. The hypothesized model is shown in Figure 1.

[INSERT FIGURE 1 HERE]

Methodology

Data Collection Procedure

In this study quantitative approach was used for designing methodology and data collection. The data-collecting approach involved distributing a questionnaire to 250 nursing staff from private sectors in Rawalpindi Islamabad. PA survey was administered to collect data from 250 private nursing employees of Pakistan specifically from the twin cities (Rawalpindi and Islamabad). The current study's sample technique used probability sampling, specifically systematic sampling, to select participants from a larger population of nurses working in the private healthcare sectors in Rawalpindi and Islamabad.

Measures

A five-likert scale was used in this study. Questionnaires for this research consist of total 28 items and there were five sections, first section was of inclusive leadership scale in which was having 4 items of Zheng et al. (2017) with the reliability of 0.932. Second part was of job embeddedness consisted of 5 items scale by Ng and Feldman (2013) having with the reliability of 0.923. Third section was of OCB consisted of 5 items scale by Ali et al. (2022) with the reliability of 0.788. And the last section was of employee resilience consisted of 12 items by K Naswall et al. (2013) with the reliability of 0.89.

Analytical Technique

The proposed data analysis approach relied on SPSS to conduct correlation analysis to investigate correlations between variables among nursing professionals in Pakistan. Pearson correlation coefficients was used to determine the strength and direction of relationships between variables such as inclusive leadership, job embeddedness, organizational citizenship behavior and employee resilience. Descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviations, and frequencies were also be generated to summarize the sample and variable characteristics. Furthermore, inferential statistics such as t-tests or ANOVA were used to evaluate whether there are statistically significant differences between groups.

Data Analysis and Results

The sample comprised 250 nurses, of whom 12.8% were male and 87.2% female. Most nurses (40%) were aged 25-31 years, followed by 22.8% aged 18-24, 16% aged 32-38, 10.4% aged 39-45, and 10.8% aged 46 or above. Regarding qualifications, 58.8% held an undergraduate diploma, 34% were graduates/BSN, and 7.2% had a

master's degree. In terms of experience, 58.8% had 1-5 years, 16.4% had 6-10 years, another 16.4% had 11-15 years, and 8.4% had 16 or more years of experience.

Descriptive Analysis

Table I portrays the distribution of means, standard deviations, and response scale range showing that the participants reported positive means for IL, OCB, JE, and ER with moderate variability, evidence by mean scores between 3.79 and 3.94, SDs between .739 and .945, and the full range of the response scale (1–5). The results of the normality test showed that all of the research scale's factors' kurtosis and skewness values fell between -2 and +2, as accepted by George and Mallery (2010).

[INSERT TABLE I HERE]

Reliability Analysis

The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of four scales inclusive leadership, job embeddedness, OCB and employee resilience were found to be greater than 0.70, which proves that the scales have acceptable reliability of .70 and above as provided by Nunnally (1978). According to George and Mallery (2003), values greater than .80 are considered good, as indicated in the table II.

[INSERT TABLE II HERE]

Correlation Analysis

The study found statistically significant positive correlations among the variables, ranging from low to strong. Inclusive leadership (IL) showed a moderate correlation with organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) ($r = .405$) and a low correlation with job embeddedness (JE) ($r = .374$) and employee resilience (ER) ($r = .340$). JE had a moderate correlation with OCB ($r = .495$) and a strong correlation with ER ($r = .695$). OCB and ER also had a moderate correlation ($r = .573$), refer to Table III. Despite some weak correlations, Eddie Seva See (2015) argues that such findings remain valuable in organizational behavior, where complex interactions often dilute direct relationships, highlighting the multifaceted nature of human behavior.

[INSERT TABLE III HERE]

Hypothesis Testing

Table IV indicates the results of direct hypothesis testing. Linear regression was applied and the results are mentioned in the above table. Hypothesis 1 postulated that there is a positive relationship between inclusive leadership and OCB. The results of regression analysis demonstrate that 16.1% of variation in OCB is being caused by inclusive leadership. Also, the model is fit for regression ($F = 32.48$, $p < 0.05$) with 0.000 value of significance. The value of coefficient ($\beta = 0.405$) indicates that one unit change in inclusive leadership will predict the 0.30 unit change in OCB. Moreover, the results also indicate significant effect of ($t = 5.696$, $p < 0.05$) inclusive leadership on OCB, hence hypothesis 1 is accepted.

Hypothesis 2 postulated that there is a positive relationship between inclusive leadership and employee resilience. The results of regression analysis demonstrate

that 11.6% of variation in employee resilience is being caused by inclusive leadership. Also, the model is fit for regression ($F = 36.48$, $p < 0.05$) with 0.000 value of significance. The value of coefficient ($\beta = 0.340$) indicates that one unit change in inclusive leadership will predict the 0.34 unit change in employee resilience. Moreover, the results also indicate significant effect of ($t = 5.699$, $p < 0.05$) inclusive leadership on employee resilience, hence hypothesis 2 is accepted.

[INSERT TABLE IV HERE]

Hypothesis 3 postulated that there is a positive relationship between inclusive leadership and job embeddedness. The results of regression analysis demonstrate that 14% of variation in job embeddedness is being caused by inclusive leadership. Also, the model is fit for regression ($F = 40.33$, $p < 0.05$) with 0.000 value of significance. The value of coefficient ($\beta = 0.374$) indicates that one unit change in inclusive leadership will predict the 0.37 unit change in job embeddedness. Moreover, the results also indicate significant effect of ($t = 6.351$, $p < 0.05$) inclusive leadership on job embeddedness, hence hypothesis 3 is accepted. Hypothesis 4 postulated that there is a positive relationship between job embeddedness and OCB. The results of regression analysis demonstrate that 25.4% of variation in OCB is being caused by job embeddedness. Also, the model is fit for regression ($F = 86.66$, $p < 0.05$) with 0.000 value of significance. The value of coefficient ($\beta = 0.495$) indicates that one unit change in job embeddedness will predict the 0.49 unit change in OCB. Moreover, the results also indicate significant effect of ($t = 8.189$, $p < 0.05$) job embeddedness on OCB, hence hypothesis 4 is accepted.

Hypothesis 6 postulated that there is a positive relationship between job embeddedness and employee resilience. The results of regression analysis demonstrate that 24.5% of variation in employee resilience is being caused by job embeddedness. Also, the model is fit for regression ($F = 80.66$, $p < 0.05$) with 0.000 value of significance. The value of coefficient ($\beta = 0.695$) indicates that one unit change in job embeddedness will predict the 0.69 unit change in employee resilience. Moreover, the results also indicate significant effect of ($t = 8.981$, $p < 0.05$) job embeddedness on employee resilience, hence hypothesis 6 is accepted.

Mediation Analysis

After testing the direct hypothesis, Mediation tests in the current study were computed in order to evaluate the mediation by using the PROCESS macro by Hayes (2013); (model 4) under the SPSS setting. This macro extends the capabilities of the mediation analysis and enables researchers to obtain the reliable estimate of both direct and indirect effects in mediation models. Particularly, the PROCESS macro delivers empirical bootstrapped confidence intervals for uniquely gauging indirect effects and improving the credibility of outcomes. This approach is commonly acknowledged as beneficial for use in social sciences among others; more information about it can be found in Hayes' information (Hayes, 2013; Hayes, 2022).

The results for total effects depicted that inclusive leadership influences OCB and the value of T is significant from all the perspectives ($\beta = 0.3049$, $t = 5.699$, $p < 0.05$, 95%CI

[0.1995, 0.4103]). Moreover, the results for direct effects depicted that inclusive leadership influences OCB in the presence of job embeddedness and the value of T is significant from all the perspectives ($\beta=0.1615$, $t=3.0820$, $p<0.05$, 95% CI [0.583,0.2647]).

Furthermore, the results for indirect effects indicated that inclusive leadership influences OCB through job embeddedness which is confirmed by the significant values ($\beta=0.1434$, 95%CI [0.0760, 0.2229]). The overall results depicted that there was a mediation effect of job embeddedness in the relationship between inclusive leadership and OCB, because the criteria of LLCI and ULCI signs and all other values are significant. So, the hypothesis 5, which was “job embeddedness positively mediates the relationship between inclusive leadership and OCB” is accepted.

[INSERT TABLE V HERE]

The results for total effects depicted that inclusive leadership influences employee resilience and the value of T is significant from all the perspectives ($\beta=0.677$, $t=7.227$, $p<0.05$, 95%CI [0.1169, 0.2524]). Moreover, the results for direct effects depicted that inclusive leadership influences employee resilience in the presence of job embeddedness and the value of T is significant from all the perspectives ($\beta=0.508$, $t=5.325$, $p<0.05$, 95% CI [0.1370,0.2385]).

Furthermore, the results for indirect effects indicated that inclusive leadership influences employee resilience through job embeddedness which is confirmed by the significant values ($\beta=0.170$, 95%CI [0.0225, 0.1005]). The overall results depicted that there was a mediation effect of job embeddedness in the relationship between inclusive leadership and employee resilience, because the criteria of LLCI and ULCI signs and all other values are significant. So, the hypothesis 7, which was “job embeddedness positively mediates the relationship between inclusive leadership and employee resilience” is accepted.

[INSERT TABLE VI HERE]

Discussion

An environment where OCB develops is greatly enhanced by inclusive leadership. The social exchange theory, which contends that when leaders foster an atmosphere of support and inclusivity, employees perceive these efforts as investments in their well-being, can be used to analyse the relationship between OCB and inclusive leadership. Reciprocal behaviours, like OCB, where workers voluntarily go above and beyond the call of duty to benefit the company, are a result of this perception (Borgia, 2022). Employee initiative, teamwork, and knowledge sharing are all fostered by this safety, which is essential to OCB. Because they feel appreciated and encouraged, workers under inclusive leadership are more likely to participate in OCB, according to research by Carmeli et al. (2010).

In order to complete their job as proactive members of the organisation, they are intrinsically motivated to return every favour they get. The team's overall OCB is improved as a result of the loyalty and trust that are fostered by inclusive leadership (Wang et al., 2018). Job embeddedness theory states that workers who have

supportive leadership and close organisational relationships are better equipped to handle difficulties because they have access to resources and emotional support (Fetter et al., 2021). By making sure that workers feel appreciated and included, inclusive leadership fosters a sense of security in them that strengthens resilience. These leaders cultivate a resilient mindset by encouraging staff members to express their worries, work together productively, and come up with solutions as a group.

According to social exchange theory, which deepens this relationship, workers learn resilience to hold onto their positions and make valuable contributions in return for their leaders' inclusivity (Mulyani, 2019). Employees under inclusive leaders report higher levels of self-efficacy and flexibility, according to empirical research (Shore et al., 2011). This is due to the fact that inclusive leaders foster a sense of empowerment and confidence in their workforce, which empowers them to tackle issues with a solution-focused perspective and use their networks to support them, so increasing their resilience (Luthans et al., 2007).

Social exchange theory provides additional insight into this link by emphasising how inclusive leadership fosters mutual respect and trust, which in turn fosters a sense of duty and improves work embeddedness (Sablinski et al., 2003). According to Ng and Feldman (2014), executives that practise inclusivity foster closer relationships within the company since it is fulfilling for workers to be a part of a culture that values them. Job embeddedness theory says that employees develop an invested belief in the success of their organisation when they feel a significant attachment to it through professional, social, and cultural bonds (Gerson et al., 2021). This is supported by social exchange theory, which shows that workers reciprocate the stability and support they receive by acting philanthropically and cooperatively (McCarthy, 2022). Because embedded employees perceive a reciprocal exchange in which their extra efforts are acknowledged and respected, studies indicate that job embeddedness corresponds with greater levels of OCB (Holtom et al., 2006). By encouraging people to keep up their OCB, this positive reinforcement helps them become even more integrated into the organisation and creates a positive feedback loop (Lee et al., 2004). The mediating role of job embeddedness between inclusive leadership and OCB can be explained by the idea that inclusive leaders create a supportive atmosphere that increases employees' embeddedness, which in turn leads to OCB. According to job embeddedness theory, employees are more likely to make a positive contribution if they feel a strong connection to their workplace and share similar values (Min et al., 2001). This is further supported by social exchange theory, which emphasises how beneficial behaviours result from the perceived fairness and trust that inclusive leadership fosters (Näswall et al., 1964). According to research by Sun and Pan (2011), job embeddedness can act as a link between increased OCB and inclusive leadership, demonstrating that workers who are more engaged in their positions are more driven to contribute more.

Strong ties to one's company allow employees to use their resources and relationships to overcome obstacles, which fosters job embeddedness and resilience. According to the job embeddedness theory, employees are more resilient in the face of adversity the more deeply they are connected to the organization (Pyszczynski et al., 2021). This

relationship is supported by social exchange theory, which shows that embedded personnel enhance their commitment and adaptability when they see reciprocal benefits from their organisation (Khaskheli et al., 2020). Because they feel safe and supported by their networks and coworkers, employees with high job embeddedness report being more resilient, according to empirical data (Qalati et al., 2019). The availability of these tools supports workers' resilience and capacity to continue producing under duress by assisting them in maintaining calm and managing stress efficiently.

According to job embeddedness theory, people who form close relationships within an organisation are more resilient because they believe they have the support they need to face obstacles head-on (Sugiyama et al., 2001). As a result, workers feel safe and encouraged, which strengthens resilience. According to social exchange theory, this dynamic stems from a sense of reciprocity; when workers get support and inclusion, they become more resilient as part of their dedication to preserving their embedded status (Tsai et al., 1964).

Conclusion

This study examined the impact of Inclusive Leadership (IL) on multiple employee outcomes, including Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), Job Embeddedness (JE), and Employee Resilience (ER), in the private healthcare sector of Rawalpindi and Islamabad. The study's goal was to gain a better understanding of how leadership techniques influence employee actions and attitudes by examining the correlations between these factors. The findings have major implications for hospital management and leadership practices, offering vital insights on how to develop a productive and resilient workforce. The findings reveal that IL has a direct and positive impact on OCB, implying that when leaders display inclusivity, employees are more eager to go beyond their ordinary job obligations. Inclusive leaders that value diversity, encourage participation, and reward achievements help to create an environment in which employees are more inclined to engage in positive behaviors that benefit their peers and the firm as a whole. This finding is consistent with earlier research that has emphasized the importance of inclusive leadership in cultivating a culture of support and collaboration.

This study found that employees who have a positive attitude regarding job attachment are more likely to engage in behaviors that improve the organization's performance. This understanding can help healthcare managers develop ways that promote job attachment through leadership practices, resulting in a more stable and engaged workforce. Furthermore, the study adds to our understanding of how IL can promote ER among employees. The findings indicate that when employees see their leaders as inclusive, they are more likely to feel job security and support, which boosts their resilience. The mediating role of JE suggests that this sense of security and attachment is critical in helping employees develop the psychological resources required to properly manage stressful conditions. From a practical standpoint, the study's findings highlight the importance of incorporating IL practices into healthcare management's leadership development programs. Organizations can establish a

healthy work environment that boosts employee job satisfaction and resilience by educating leaders to practice inclusive behaviors such as active listening appreciating multiple opinions, and fostering open communication.

Implications

The outcomes of this research present valuable implications for both practice and theory, particularly in the context of healthcare systems operating under limited resources, such as those in Pakistan. Practically, the study underscores the critical role of inclusive leadership in nurturing behaviors like organizational citizenship and enhancing employee resilience. When leaders actively involve staff in decisions, recognize their contributions, and foster an inclusive environment, employees are more likely to feel valued, leading to greater motivation and willingness to exceed formal job duties. The research also identifies job embeddedness as a significant factor that mediates the relationship between leadership and employee outcomes. Healthcare organizations that invest in career development, encourage peer support, and align individual and organizational values can strengthen employees' emotional and professional attachment, reducing turnover and enhancing resilience. From a theoretical perspective, the study contributes to the understanding of social exchange theory and job embeddedness theory by illustrating their relevance in high-stress, service-oriented environments. The findings reveal how leadership styles influence employee behavior through relational and contextual mechanisms, offering a deeper insight into workforce dynamics. Future studies may expand on this framework by examining other variables or testing the model across different organizational settings to enrich the field's theoretical foundations.

Limitations and Future Research Recommendations

The study's cross-sectional design limited the ability to establish causality among Inclusive Leadership (IL), Job Embeddedness (JE), Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), and Employee Resilience (ER). Longitudinal studies are recommended to track changes over time and provide deeper insights. The focus on private healthcare sector nurses in Rawalpindi and Islamabad restricts the findings' generalizability to other regions, industries, or employee populations, as leadership styles and dynamics may vary. Self-reported data collection via questionnaires may have introduced biases like social desirability, potentially affecting accuracy. While the sample size was statistically adequate, larger samples could enhance reliability, allow advanced analyses, and enable multi-group comparisons to explore demographic or organizational disparities.

Future research should incorporate longitudinal designs to examine causal correlations and explore IL's influence across diverse industries, organizational cultures, and sectors. Investigating additional leadership styles, such as Transformational, Servant, or Authentic Leadership, could offer a broader perspective on their effects on JE, OCB, and ER. Exploring the moderating role of organizational culture or individual personality traits may reveal how factors like teamwork and

transparency amplify IL's impact on outcomes, offering valuable insights for optimizing leadership strategies.

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